

Preparing Students for the 4th Industrial Revolution at St. Edward's University

Introduction

The [Institute for Interdisciplinary Science](#), also known as i4, at [St. Edward's University](#) was established in 2018 with support from a [National Science Foundation \(NSF\)](#) grant ([Award #1832282](#)) to develop industry-academic partnerships to enhance undergraduate STEM education and establish research collaborations with faculty. Upon the expiration of the NSF grant, i4 has concentrated on its most impactful initiative, which is offering paid, summer internships to undergraduate STEM majors. i4 has placed nearly 100 students in summer internships at local and national organizations since its founding. For program directors seeking to establish or transition an internship program at their institution, i4 offers a clear example of how to sustain impactful student opportunities beyond the life of a grant.

Program Structure and Offerings

Situated within the [School of Natural Sciences](#), i4 is structured as a multidisciplinary hub that engages with external partners to provide paid summer internships for 10 to 20 rising juniors and seniors who are majoring in a STEM discipline each year. In a typical year, about 20% of eligible students apply for internships through i4, reflecting the program's positive reputation and popularity among STEM students. The internships prepare students for future careers by exposing them to job responsibilities, budgetary constraints, technical knowledge needed for managing projects, and building their work experience.

INTERSHIP DETAILS:

- **Duration:** Summer internships last between 8 and 12 weeks.
- **Eligibility:** Participating majors include computer science, biology, chemistry, mathematics, forensic sciences, and applied data science and kinesiology. After the

expiration of NSF funding and the transition to donor funding, this allowed the opportunity for international students to apply. Specific eligibility requirements for international applicants vary by partner, and i4 does not introduce additional eligibility requirements on their end

- **Location:** Internships are completed remotely or on-site. Internships that require students to be on-site are typically located in Austin, TX and the surrounding area.
- **Projects:** When submitting an application to i4, students select and rank companies and projects based on their interests.
- **Review Process:** Students apply directly to i4 and applicants are assessed by i4 based on GPAs, experience, specialized training, demonstrated communication skills, and reference letters. The assessment is done by the i4 team, which counts as service towards tenure/promotion.
- **Student compensation:** Interns receive a base pay rate of \$650 per week (subject to applicable taxes), with the expectation of working full-time (40 hours/week) for the duration of the internship (10-12 weeks). However, employers sometimes choose to increase the pay, or employ for a longer period of time. i4 covers the base pay rate for 5 weeks, regardless of what the employer chooses. All modifications are the responsibility of the employer.

With funding from the NSF, i4 covered the full cost of salaries for interns. Upon the expiration of the grant, external partners have been asked to cover at least 50% of internship salaries. The remaining costs have been supported by private donors.

KEY RESOURCES AND SUPPORT:

- A Corporate and Foundations Relations (CFR) team to outreach potential partners and donors and assist in event planning.
- Support from the Dean of the School of Natural Sciences to champion the program and outreach and engage donors.
- A successful alumni network that is willing to facilitate introductions to potential sponsors and share their positive experience with prospective students.
- A dedicated point of contact to outreach, onboard partners, and answer questions from students and partners.
- Donations from University alumni.

Partnership Development

Each year, i4 works with 5 to 10 external partners to create internship opportunities for its students. Internships are not required to have a data-intensive training component, however, most internships do. Examples include [National Ecological Observatory Network \(NEON\)](#) [Battelle](#), where students have built and upgraded dashboards and R packages to manage data

collection by NEON scientists; [Valkyrie](#), where students have developed a data-driven system designed to streamline and accelerate the process of matching participants with volunteers and vice versa; and [The Nature Conservancy](#), where students assisted scientists with managing, analyzing and monitoring research data. These examples illustrate the wide range of impactful, data-oriented projects that students contribute to through i4 internships. Securing these kinds of opportunities depends on i4's proactive efforts to build and sustain relationships with external partners.

STRATEGIES FOR PARTNERSHIP DEVELOPMENT:

i4 develops partnerships through three primary strategies: (1) alumni networks, (2) St. Edward's faculty networks, and (3) campus leadership and outreach teams.

1. ALUMNI NETWORKS

Engaging alumni networks has proven to be an effective strategy for developing external partnerships for i4 internships. Alumni who have directly benefited from the program understand its value and are often eager to support its continued success. Alumni can authentically speak to the program's impact and can serve as powerful advocates in encouraging their employers to partner with i4. Alumni also attract prospective students as they share their positive experiences with their peers.

2. FACULTY NETWORKS

i4 engages faculty within the School of Natural Sciences through monthly lunch events. During these events, faculty are invited to share ideas and facilitate connections to potential partners. This regular engagement fosters a culture of collaboration and ensures faculty play an active role in expanding the program's network of opportunities. This also allows i4 to keep regular tabs on how past interns (whether current students or alumni) are progressing. This is valuable information both for determining the success of the program, but also for contacting new partners when the students graduate and take full-time positions.

3. CAMPUS LEADERSHIP AND OUTREACH TEAMS

The Dean of the School of Natural Sciences and the CFR team within the Office of University Advancement at St. Edward's have been a critical resource for connections to external partners and donors. Their established relationships with industry and community organizations provide the program with a trusted entry point to new collaborations. Additionally, their active advocacy for i4 helps reinforce the program's credibility and attract sustained interest from potential partners and donors.

PROCESS AT A GLANCE

1. i4 reaches out to potential partners early each fall.

2. Interested partners share job descriptions and a list of qualifications that they are seeking in student interns, such as experience with specific software or experience in a lab.
3. i4 reviews students' application materials and offers recommendations to partners for candidates who should advance to the interview stage.
4. External partners conduct interviews and make final decisions regarding hiring.

Student Preparation

Students are selected to proceed to the interview process based on their technical preparation and experience that best fit with project and job descriptions shared by partnering organizations. On average, well over 50% of students who apply and satisfy minimum satisfactory criteria (e.g., selected positions relevant to their degree; no red-flags in faculty recommendation letters) receive a job offer. Students who do not secure an offer will receive follow-up from the i4 team explaining how they could improve their application the following year.

Once students have secured an offer for an internship, i4 provides the students with guidance on professional etiquette such as punctuality and communication, while the Chief Risk Officer (CRO) at St. Edward's University provides an overview of confidentiality and noncompete agreements. The CRO and their team continue to serve as a resource for students as they navigate agreements but the ultimate decision to sign any documents rests on students. The guidance is shared during a synchronous virtual meeting, with attendance required for all interns.

Benefits & Outcomes

i4 has established a successful track record for recruiting and matching talented students with external partners who are seeking interns for specialized projects. The internships offer a critical opportunity for students to apply their skills to real-world problems while gaining a clearer sense of career pathways they may want to pursue upon graduation. Partners benefit from early access to a talent pipeline while the university strengthens communities and makes meaningful contributions to research innovations, locally and nationally.

- **For students:** Experience applying technical skills to solve real-world problems and a high likelihood of securing subsequent internships and a job upon graduation.
- **For faculty:** Opportunities to advocate for students, shape i4 programming, and learn about workforce needs to inform curriculum.
- **For employers:** Early access to a skilled workforce that includes many who are the first in their families to attend college, resulting in a positive generational and community impact that amplifies the long-term benefits of each internship experience.
- **For St. Edward's:** Positive reputation as a forward-looking institution that prepares students for careers while uplifting communities through partnerships rooted in service and shared prosperity.

Challenges & Future Directions

A primary challenge for i4 has been ensuring financial sustainability following the expiration of its NSF grant. Like many innovative programs, i4 depends on continued institutional support and external funding to maintain its partnerships. Post the NSF grant which initiated i4, this external funding has taken the form of donor funds. These limited resources have been concentrated on i4's core strength which is recruiting and matching skilled students for summer internships. Given the mutual benefits of partnerships and the positive impact on students and the community, partnering organizations now cover at least 50% of internship salaries with some partners offering to cover more. Looking ahead, i4 aims to continue diversifying its funding sources through donations, grants, and sponsorships to achieve sustainability.

Practical Guidance for Program Leaders

i4 at St. Edward's University offers several insights for program leaders who are developing or scaling experiential, mission-driven initiatives that prepare students for careers in a rapidly evolving labor market.

1. **Leverage campus resources:** Identify and engage people on campus who can help make connections to donors, sponsors, and employers to build a pipeline of supporters and partners.
2. **Build a strong alumni network:** Cultivate relationships with alumni, as they play a critical role in recruiting students and facilitating connections with employers.
3. **Ask for help:** Don't hesitate to seek assistance from colleagues and staff. Faculty often take on decision-making alone, but asking for help can uncover untapped expertise and support that deduplicates processes and frees up resources.
4. **Embrace growth even amid financial uncertainty:** Expanding a program can feel risky when funding is limited, but high demand and strong results often attract university support and external funding.
5. **Focus on program strengths:** Identify the most successful aspects of your program early, and prioritize them. Pursuing less effective initiatives can consume valuable resources.
6. **Simplify partnership agreements:** Fewer clauses reduce points of friction and prevent potential delays.

Contact

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